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Editorial

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Many exciting research studies in Science today lie at the interface between various disciplines. The interface between Chemistry and Biology is particularly rich, since it closely reflects Nature and the origins of Life. Multiple research groups in the Chemistry Departments around the world have made substantial efforts to interweave ideas from Chemistry and Biology to solve important questions related to material science and healthcare, just to name a few. International Journal of Bioorganic Chemistry & Molecular Biology is helping to define this evolving approach to Science. Interfacial research on Chemistry and Biology is exceptionally broad in scope, extending from the rational design and synthesis of organic molecules binding and affecting function of specific nucleic acid and protein targets, to the spectroscopic studies of bio-molecular structures and the development of new nano-tools and polymeric biomaterials for drug delivery. In general, research articles published in the International Journal of Bioorganic Chemistry & Molecular Biology are focused on synthesizing

compounds and materials with novel biological activity, developing new experimental and spectroscopic techniques to characterize biomolecules and biological phenomena, and to demonstrate potential applications of the synthetic molecules and materials. As this type of research is inherently collaborative, many articles describe joint projects between Chemistry and Molecular Biology Departments in the different parts of the world. In such an interactive environment, sharing specialized ideas and continually exploring new research opportunities across Natural Sciences, promotes the rapid development of multiple research fields including nano-biotechnology, material science, molecular diagnostics and therapy of human diseases.

Conclusion

Interfacing and implementing ideas from both Chemistry and Biology in order to speed up and expand studies and problem solving within certain fields such as, material science and healthcare, requires the ability of researchers to share specialized ideas while continually exploring new research opportunities within the interface of Natural Sciences. Being an international Open Access journal dedicated to the latest advancement of Bioorganic Chemistry and Molecular Biology, the International Journal of Bioorganic Chemistry & Molecular Biology offers such an opportunity. It publishes original research, applied, and educational articles in all areas of Bioorganic Chemistry and Molecular Biology that corresponds to a very broad range of interests and audience of readers.

References

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